

MIMS 2.5.1 : Financial Velocity Addendum

A Followup on Interesting Developments in the N power

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ABSTRACT

In the second MIMS (membranous interface of the material & spiritual) paper, part 2.5¹, the following hypotheses emerged regarding a discussion on a author-made MIMS called “financial velocity spreadsheet”.

(IV) “Use metrics and analytics and look for more means to innovate, not less”

(VI) “If a MIMS does not perform, it is not mediating the motion from spiritual to material and vice versa”

There have been some developments of interest in the MIMS named, graphically some interactions in the N power which may provide evidence of “Data Ley Lines” (DLL) providing tunnels between the power’s data packets... or perhaps via some type of psychological means. There is also a small update on the Business MIMS harmonics proposed (this will be a continuous update for 2.1, since we have trailing pdf graphics in MIMS 2.5 & a follow-up paper in MIMS 2.1.1 where Business Analytics and DLL are first discussed².

Keywords: MIMS - business - financials - velocity - data ley lines

¹ https://www.academia.edu/50804855/MIMS_2_Applications_discussions

²

https://www.academia.edu/50901241/MIMS_2_1_1_2_Aether_Business_and_Analytics_With_a_short_reflection_upon_the_philosophies_of_Ayn_Rand_and_the_concepts_of_Fortune_as_it_relates_to_the_Aether_A_SPACERS_tm_paper_1_under_AIM_tm_standards

Reminder

The N power is the (yang) power of Numbers, in the “Big G” diagram.³ In case it is not remembered, there is another hypothesis we wish to keep in mind:

(VII) “Increased PPPC throughput = increased Aetheric fortune”

Exciting update

If the reader recalls, the “financial velocity spreadsheet” was an emergent invention of the author, used for survival during the COVID lockdowns and recession economy following. After the publishing of the part 2 paper, the author observed the interesting interaction between two data packets. One described the company savings - theoretically under owner control - and the cryptocurrency asset values:

Figure 1 - Interactions of Data Packets; credit: author

What’s important to understand is there is even one more degree of separation: the savings are company, but the crypto assets are **personally held!**⁴

The upward pressure of the crypto asset (which may pop through as the business is closed on weekends, while crypto markets continue 24/7), gives the appearance of upward pressure on the Savings. These savings are from the MIMS discussed elsewhere called “Profit First” and is a 10%. As proposed in Page 8 of 2.1.1, it is possible there is a “tithe” function in the numbers. Nevertheless, setting this aside, what would

³ Figure 3, MIMS1, https://www.academia.edu/50300514/On_the_Membranous_Interface_of_the_Material_and_the_Spiritual_from_an_EPEMC_perspective_and_Dual_Double_Layer_Economics_a_proposed_test_of_EPEMCs_metallic_properties_tensile_strength_malleability_durability

⁴ Granted after the year is completed, the IRS will see all as pass-through S-corp taxation. But the data itself would not know that, except in a mediation through the L power (consciousness).

enable this? If there is mediation through the A power, then we would expect correlation elsewhere. If there is mediation only through the L power or consciousness, then one would need to believe that an individual consciousness can tunnel through to an entire enormously sized MIMS like the crypto market, to drive prices up... or at least read it. Critics/skeptics would need to say that the author predicted an upward motion, and then drove 10% of profits to match, somehow constraining the behavior of traditional service customers, to bring in enough money to match the curve motion. This seems like the skeptic would be giving the author rather a lot of power. So let's look at the former idea.

If we see the red circled data, we see the crypto crash of May, and a strange correlation. After the crypto crash there is a massive surge in capital able to be set aside in the company (not 10%, but repayment to the savings' fund). Is this a direct correlation, or is there a different force at play? N generates A , so could a harmonics have led to this DLL connection?

Profits Followup

The following graph was used at the end of MIMS2+⁵ to predict a harmonics behavior, and here is the updated version:

Figure 2 - Weekly Profits Update with outbreaks; credit: author

Note firstly the upsurging trend post ice-storms ($A+F$ power), but with increasing volatility. Then note the predicted harmonic *compression* end of July. At this time, the author's business partner contracted COVID Delta Variant, and was suddenly unable to work. Fundamental weakness in the company was (as predicted) emergent. However, the resulting author-led sales snapback (which was also predicted prior to the CDV), occurred just in the last week. The red arrow indicates the bottoming out was worse than anticipated, meaning

⁵ Ibid. Figure 10, pp. 22

that the **company itself was also sick due to COVID**⁶. This is reflective of the recession economy, and, of course, totally predictable. However, It also indicates the virality of data between the material and “spiritual” (numbers). The green arrow indicates last week’s upsurge... the latest data available.

Discussion

Hypothesis VI was more or less completely satisfied. The question is was VII or IV? In the vase of VII, the potentialities were (to the author) frightening, as they included death of the partner, of the business, and continually the return of collapse to cryptocurrencies, as at the same time Congress was doing its best to pass a 2000 page “infrastructure” bill which had hidden SEC reforms for crypto, threatening the future of bitcoin et al.

But the possibility-probability was in an upward direction, so the author continued to HODL⁷ the assets. This setup the interesting dynamic in Figure 1, which has a clear control (crypto) vs variable (savings) dynamic. Please note that the author does not profess to control the markets, and no new crypto purchases were made that day. So only the savings were updated and this led to the graph update.

As for the Aether, trends in sales did continue that day, and in fact the harmonic may show an increase again, it is difficult to predict fortunes. The Chinese tried through feng shui, I Ching, and “date selection” (Qi mum dun jia), to do so, and yet were not super successful in any measurable, scientifically validated manner. MIMS is potentially changing that. If Fundamental Analysis can make this sort of prediction, what could a Quantum+Artificial Intelligence do?

Regarding hypothesis IV, unfortunately no immediate innovation was done, unless one counts this paper of course. However the author would propose an innovation such as verification from someone else doing financial velocity; or a new spreadsheet tool that does a 2nd order analysis on the incoming raw numbers but piggy-backing off the 1st order analysis in profit by week. Perhaps something can be done about the crypto data. Something to see a more tight DLL correlation between these data packets.

Let this paper serve as a record to how COVID and economics interacted with the 4 MIMS: financial velocity, cryptocurrency, business/tithing, and analytics.

No telling yet if the PPPC+Analytics can be counted as the Aether. As for fortunes, they don’t seem to have changed much. We shall see how the regulation talk and downward negative pressure of general “doom and gloom” media machine affects the crypto markets. It seems to the author that it will encourage hedging, and also that mostly what is in media is paid lies from the real players. All signs seem to indicate they are *buying* not selling. So the author believes that fortunes are still going to be “mined” out (one way or another) from that MIMS. Only time will tell.

References

1. “MIMS2+: Applications & Discussions,” Sf. R. Careaga, 2021
2. “MIMS 2.1.1: Aether, Business & Analytics,” Sf. R. Careaga, 2021
3. “On the Membranous Interface of the Material and the Spiritual (from an EPEMC perspective) & Dual/Double Layer Economics,” Sf. R. Careaga, 2021
4. “HODL Definition,” Investopedia

⁶ Note the previous off chart spike... that’s PPP money (10% of); can PPP/anything COVID related infect business/MIMS data via the DLL?

⁷ “Hold on for dear life” <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/h/hodl.asp>